

A novel framework for studying oceanic freshwater transports, and its application in discerning the modelled fate of freshwater around the coast of Greenland

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ABSTRACT

In the sub-polar North Atlantic, the accumulation of fresh meltwaters from Greenland and the Arctic can impact the strength of the climatically important Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. In this study I investigate and map out the processes that contribute to the accumulation of freshwater in four different regions around Greenland, quantifying horizontal transports of freshwater and the expansion and depletion of freshwater reservoirs by surface sources and interior mixing. Rather than using traditional freshwater budgets, whose flaws are well documented, I propose the novel use of the freshwater transformation framework and apply it to outputs from an eddy resolving coupled climate model (10 km atmosphere and 5 km ocean).

Analysing volume transports in salinity space we observe the salinification of the boundary currents surrounding Greenland as they flow from Fram Strait towards the Labrador Sea. Using the freshwater transformation framework we are able to link the salinification to mixing, sea-ice formation or the accumulation of freshwaters stored in the waters surrounding Greenland. The balance changes depending upon the region and season under question. The mixing of freshwaters is found to be stronger during wintertime than in summertime. Furthermore, mixing plays a more dominant role in the freshwater transformation budget off Southern Greenland, where sea-ice cover is low, than off Northern Greenland, where sea-ice cover is high.

1. Introduction

Many climate models predict that the climatically important Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is sensitive to perturbations in the freshwater cycle around the coast of Greenland (Jackson et al., 2023). It is expected that there will be large changes in the freshwater cycle in the sub-polar North Atlantic over the coming years as a result of anthropogenic climate change — the melting of the Greenland Ice Sheet is predicted to become a dominant freshwater source in the region, for instance (Lenaerts et al., 2015). Due to the AMOC's influence on the climate of Northern Europe and North America (Jackson et al., 2015; Buckley and Marshall, 2016; Bryden et al., 2020), understanding how the AMOC responds to such perturbations is a question with societal importance.

Model limitations when it comes to the representation of the climatological-mean freshwater cycle around Greenland have hindered our ability to predict the sensitivity of the AMOC to perturbations in the freshwater cycle (Weijer et al., 2012; Swingedouw et al., 2022). Coarse resolution climate models, such as those contributing to CMIP6, struggle to correctly represent features such as the high-latitude boundary currents which surround Greenland for example (Duyck, 2023).

These are a key pathway of freshwaters from the Arctic to the sub-polar North Atlantic (Dukhovskoy et al., 2016). It has been hoped that “next-generation”, eddy rich climate models may do a much better job of representing the pathways of freshwater around Greenland (Hirschi et al., 2020). Studies using eddy resolving forced ocean and regional models have already identified improvements in the horizontal pathways of freshwater (Swingedouw et al., 2022; Weijer et al., 2012); however, the spatio-temporal patterns of diahaline mixing rates (which deplete reservoirs of low salinity waters) in such models have yet to be mapped out. Doing so is pertinent as it can help us to understand whether there are certain regions around Greenland's coast which may be particularly sensitive to perturbations in the freshwater cycle, in both models and the real ocean.

In this study I will highlight the benefits of using the “freshwater transformation framework” in describing freshwater pathways, and apply it to outputs from an eddy resolving climate model to explore modelled freshwater pathways around Greenland. Using the framework we will be able to identify some of the model's limitations and explore how the ocean responds to inputs of freshwater in a way that conventional frameworks, such as freshwater transport frameworks (e.g.

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Fig. 1. Sketch of the sub-polar North Atlantic and boundary current circulations. Grey contour shows the 1000 m isobath in the SRTM30_PLUS data product (Becker et al., 2009). Blue and orange contours show the sea-ice edge (defined as 15% sea-ice cover) during March and September respectively, in the OSI-SAF sea-ice product (OSI SAF, 2017) for the period 1979 to 1999. Current pathways are schematic only. Exchange pathways between the currents are not shown, nor are the West Greenland Coastal Current and Labrador Coastal Current which sit onshore of the West Greenland Current and Labrador Current, respectively.

Talley et al., 2011), would not allow — a key finding is the large spatio-temporal variability of diahaline mixing rates around Greenland.

In the remainder of the introduction, I will outline the need for a vocabulary to discuss the fate of fresh waters that is different to that provided by traditional freshwater transport based frameworks. In Section 2, I will introduce the freshwater transformation framework which I hope to convince you provides such a vocabulary, and in Section 3, I describe the model I demonstrate the framework on. In Section 4, I use the freshwater transformation framework to explore the modelled fate of freshwater around the coast of Greenland. I make closing remarks in Section 5.

1.1. On the need to understand where freshwaters are mixed

The surface limb of the AMOC transports waters in the Atlantic northwards, towards the sub-polar North Atlantic. Here they experience strong buoyancy forcing, resulting in the formation of dense North Atlantic Deep Waters (e.g. Marshall and Schott, 1999). As a result of anthropogenic climate change the surface limb of the AMOC is predicted

to both warm and freshen (e.g. Maroon et al., 2018; Nobre et al., 2023). To transform these more buoyant waters into North Atlantic Deep Waters requires further cooling than if they had undergone no heating or freshening, leading to a reduction in the rate of deep water formation and hence a reduction in the strength of the AMOC (Wright and Stocker, 1991; Johnson et al., 2019; Roberts et al., 2020; Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). Whether buoyancy anomalies remain fresh and confined to the surface ocean or are mixed throughout the water column can impact the depth of maximal overturning of the AMOC, which in turn alters the strength of the AMOC itself (Bonan et al., 2025). To understand the AMOC response to the heterogeneous melting of the Greenland Ice Sheet it is pertinent to also understand any heterogeneity in the mixing of freshwater inputs to the Ocean.

Hosing experiments, in which freshwater is artificially added to the North Atlantic to trigger changes in the AMOC, can be used to estimate how sensitive the AMOC is to the freshening of its surface limb. In the North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project (NA-HosMIP; Jackson et al., 2023), two hosing protocols are outlined. In one, freshwater is input uniformly across the North Atlantic, and

in the second, the addition of freshwater is concentrated around the Greenland coast. Both protocols involve temporally constant hosing fluxes. The AMOC was found to be more sensitive to freshwater hosing in simulations which hosed the whole of the North Atlantic when compared to the Greenland hosing simulations, suggesting that (1) both inefficient pathways of freshwater from source to deep water formation regions and (2) salinity changes within these waters along the way may control the response of the AMOC to freshwater hosing. [Ma et al. \(2024\)](#) additionally demonstrate that the AMOC in a (relatively coarse) model is more sensitive to freshwater inputs in the Irminger Sea than inputs in the Nordic seas, Labrador Sea or North Atlantic. Both the [Jackson et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Ma et al. \(2024\)](#) studies highlight the sensitivity of the AMOC to the location of freshwater inputs in the sub-polar North Atlantic. If we wish to develop a mechanistic understanding of how the AMOC responds to freshwater inputs in different regions, it is pertinent to understand regional differences in the fate of freshwater; for example, are there regions in which freshwater is strongly mixed, forms a freshwater lid, or is rapidly flushed away from its source sites?

1.2. Sources and pathways of freshwater around the coast of Greenland

The low salinity waters surrounding Greenland have a diverse set of sources, ranging from sea-ice, icebergs, runoff from the Greenland ice sheet, the Arctic and, to a lesser extent, atmospheric fluxes (e.g. [Haine et al., 2015](#); [Jones et al., 2008](#); [Tang et al., 2004](#)). Presently, both observations and models suggest that the majority of freshwater around North East Greenland comes from Arctic, rather than Greenland Ice Sheet meltwaters ([Foukal et al., 2020](#)). Freshwaters then follow western boundary currents around the East Coast of Greenland, with transports of liquid freshwater off the East Greenland shelf being limited ([Duyck and De Jong, 2023](#)), especially transports of glacial meltwaters ([Beaird et al., 2023](#)). Freshwaters continue to follow boundary current pathways around Cape Farewell (see [Fig. 1](#) for a sketch of the circulation of the sub-polar North Atlantic region), becoming more saline as they propagate westwards — it has been suggested this could be the result of shelf-interior exchanges ([Foukal and Pickart, 2023](#)). Of the freshwaters crossing the OSNAP East line (Overturning in the Sub-polar North Atlantic Program), around 70% of the transport occurs in the East Greenland Current system around Cape Farewell ([Le Bras et al., 2018](#)). Having reached Cape Farewell, the East Greenland Current becomes the West Greenland Current, meanders and bifurcates. Some waters continue along the coast, whereas others rim the northern edge of the Labrador Sea ([Lin et al., 2018](#); [Gou et al., 2022](#)). Meanders in the West Greenland Current have been linked to baroclinic instability and enhanced heat fluxes into the Labrador Sea ([Pacini and Pickart, 2022](#)). Using a $1/60^\circ$ model, [Gou et al. \(2022\)](#) show that exchanges of freshwater between the West Greenland Current and the interior of the Labrador Sea are limited, with the majority of freshwater exchanged ending up in the Northern Labrador Sea. Of the freshwaters within the Labrador Sea, it is estimated around 60% arrive via the boundary currents of West Greenland, rather than via Baffin Bay ([Schulze Chretien and Frajka-Williams, 2018](#)). All of this may paint a comprehensive picture of how freshwater is transported from the Arctic and the coast of Greenland through the Greenland Current systems; however, a quantitative description of both the mechanisms and salt sources which salinify these freshwaters along the way is lacking.

Additional freshwater makes its way into and out of the ocean surrounding Greenland via sea-ice melt and formation. When sea-ice is formed, brine is rejected from the ice leading to the salinification of the liquid waters left behind ([Worster and Rees Jones, 2015](#)). Sea-ice melt releases freshwater back into the ocean and dilutes the waters. In March time, when sea-ice extent is at its greatest, sea-ice cover typically extends along the East Greenland coast to Cape Farewell,

reducing in offshore extent towards the south — in [Fig. 1](#), the sea-ice edge during March and September is depicted by the blue and orange contours, respectively ([OSI SAF, 2017](#)). On the West coast, Baffin Bay is covered in sea-ice; however, cover over the interior of the Labrador Sea remains less than about 50% (see for example [Fig. 4d](#); [OSI SAF, 2017](#)). During summertime, waters south of Nares Strait have low sea-ice cover and south of Davis and Denmark Straits waters are almost completely ice free ([Roach and Meier, 2024](#); [Gloersen et al., 1992](#)). Fractional sea-ice cover from Denmark Strait to Svalbard is low and the Arctic Ocean typically remains covered by sea-ice, though its thickness decreases ([Roach and Meier, 2024](#); [Meier and Stroeve, 2022](#); [Gloersen et al., 1992](#)).

A further source of freshwater is runoff from the Greenland Ice Sheet. Integrating runoff rates from the [Bamber et al. \(2018\)](#) dataset over the shaded regions of [Fig. 2a](#), I estimate a time mean liquid freshwater flux of 26 mSv over the period 1959 to 1979 across the region of the present study. [Bamber et al. \(2018\)](#) highlight that the strength of the runoff varies with location around Greenland: runoff rates are larger on the Western coast of Greenland than on the Eastern coast, and are also larger in the north than the south. The complex circulation around Greenland means that where runoff enters the ocean affects its subsequent transport pathways and the evolution of its salinity along them (e.g. [Ma et al., 2024](#); [Dukhovskoy et al., 2016](#)). There is a strong seasonal cycle in runoff rates, which peak between June and August. Peak values are typically five times the annual mean ([Bamber et al., 2018](#)).

Precipitation and evaporation rates are typically much smaller in the coastal waters off Greenland. Off the East Coast of Greenland, inshore of the 400 m isobath, [Le Bras et al. \(2021\)](#) estimate net annual mean freshwater inputs of 1 mSv from evaporation and precipitation, 10 mSv from runoff (including iceberg melt) and 41 mSv of sea-ice melt and formation between 2000 and 2018.

1.3. Failures of freshwater transport based frameworks

When describing freshwater pathways and processes, it is typical to use frameworks which talk of freshwater transports and freshwater content (e.g. [Talley et al., 2011](#)). Recent studies have highlighted the limitations of these frameworks ([Schauer and Losch, 2019](#); [Bacon et al., 2015](#); [Treguier et al., 2014](#)). The purpose of this study is not re-litigate past arguments; however, to describe and demonstrate a framework that addresses the shortcomings described by others. It is nevertheless useful to quickly outline some of the problems with freshwater transport frameworks.

Consider a section in the ocean which has saline water flowing through it. The salinity at the section, S , and velocity through the section, v_{\perp} , vary as a function of depth, z , and the along section coordinate, x . The freshwater transport, T , through the section is defined as

$$T = - \iint_{\text{section}} v_{\perp} \frac{S - S_{ref}}{S_{ref}} dx dz. \quad (1)$$

The freshwater transport is the velocity through the section multiplied by the salinity anomaly relative to some reference salinity S_{ref} . If we have a fresh anomaly being transported through our section, we would measure a freshwater export, as we'd expect. Now consider a salty anomaly being transported in the opposite direction (the signs of the velocity and salinity anomaly are both reversed) — we would also measure a freshwater export. A real limitation of freshwater transports is that they do not distinguish between transports of saline and fresh waters.

To overcome the indistinguishability of saline imports and fresh exports when using Eq. (1), some have advocated the integral be

taken only over the parts of the section where the salinity is fresher than S_{ref} (see for example, [de Steur et al., 2017](#)). In principle, this allows us to distinguish fresh and saline transports; however, it makes comparisons between studies which use different reference salinities impossible. Should we wish to calculate freshwater transports relative to a different reference salinity using Eq. (1), we need to know only the reference salinity used in the original calculation, and the total salt and volume transports across the section. Were we to modify the definition of freshwater transport by integrating only transports of waters fresher than the reference salinity, switching reference salinities becomes impossible without knowing the full salinity and velocity fields at the section.

Adoption of a consistent reference salinity across studies would eliminate the need to recalculate freshwater transports based on different reference salinities; however, [Schauer and Losch \(2019\)](#) point out there is no unique choice for a scientifically useful reference salinity. [Bacon et al. \(2015\)](#) argue that the most appropriate reference salinity to be used when calculating freshwater transports across a section is the section averaged salinity. [Schauer and Losch \(2019\)](#) note that this value will change with region, season, under climate change, and in the case of modelling studies depend upon model biases. This makes interpreting freshwater transports across different studies difficult. [Tsubouchi et al. \(2024, 2012\)](#) demonstrate that when integrating freshwater transports around a closed region, the transports are relatively insensitive to the choice of reference salinity; rather, it is when looking at the transport at sections that do not enclose a region that problems arise. This still leaves us without a way to quantify and compare transports of low salinity waters through open gateways. [Schauer and Losch \(2019\)](#) recommend that any framework used in place of freshwater transports should be free of reference salinities and respect the principles of the conservation of salt and the conservation of mass.

In the following section I will describe the freshwater transformation framework (based on the water mass transformation framework of [Walín, 1982](#)); a framework which improves upon some of the failures of freshwater transport based frameworks. The transformation framework is free of reference salinities and built around the conservation of mass and salt as [Schauer and Losch \(2019\)](#) suggest. Furthermore, we will see it fulfils the requirements described in the present work, of being able to distinguish between transports of fresh and saline waters, and identify regions where low salinity waters are transformed into saltier waters. Finally, it retains some useful features of freshwater transport frameworks: the ability to distinguish between transports by steady and eddy motions and the ability to distinguish between different sources of freshwater (e.g. sea-ice melt, runoff). Similar frameworks have been successfully employed in studying basin [Evans et al. \(2023\)](#), estuarine ([Burchard et al., 2021](#)) and global scale circulations ([Zika et al., 2012](#)); however, use of the framework at the coastal scale; to distinguish the fate of different freshwater sources; or to distinguish between steady and eddy salinity space transports is not routine.

2. The freshwater transformation framework

Consider an arbitrary region in the ocean which is bounded by the ocean surface, an open boundary and an isohaline, S . We denote the physical volume enclosed in the region with \mathcal{V} . (A sketch of this setup is shown in [Fig. 3](#).) If we make the Boussinesq approximation, the conservation of mass in the region becomes equivalent to the conservation of volume. The conservation of volume in this region states that the tendency of the region's volume is balanced by lateral imports and exports of water fresher than S at the open boundary,

fluxes of low salinity waters at the ocean surface and diahaline volume transports. Mathematically we have

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{V}}{\partial t} = \Psi(S) + \sum_i R_i(S) + G(S) \quad (2)$$

where $\Psi(S)$ is the volume transport of water fresher than S into the region at the lateral boundaries (also known as the salinity space transport), $R_i(S)$ represents volume fluxes of waters fresher than S at the surface, and $G(S)$ represents the diahaline volume flux across the isohaline of salinity S . The index i represents different surface sources of freshwater and would typically correspond to one of evaporation, precipitation, runoff, or sea-ice melt or formation; however, any surface process associated with a liquid flux of known salinity could be incorporated into the framework.

As well as volume, the total mass of salt within the region is conserved:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^S \frac{\partial \mathcal{V}}{\partial S} S \, dS = \int_0^S \left[\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial S} S + \sum_i \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial S} S_i \right] dS - F(S) \quad (3)$$

where F is the total salt flux across an isohaline. The ∂_S operator in the above generates volume fluxes in infinitesimally thin salinity classes, with the multiplication by salinity converting this into a salt flux within that class. We will now make the ansatz that the diahaline salt flux can be expressed as the sum of an advective flux and diffusive flux. That is

$$F(S) = D(S) + SG(S), \quad (4)$$

where D is the diffusive salt flux and the final term results from advection of salt across an isohaline surface. (Recall that $G(S)$ can be interpreted as the volume flux across the isohaline surface.)

Differentiating both conservation equations with respect to salinity and substituting the resulting volume conservation equation into the salt conservation equation we find we can express the diahaline volume flux as

$$G(S) = \underbrace{-\frac{\partial D}{\partial S}}_{G_{int}} + \sum_i (S - S_i) \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial S} \quad (5)$$

We interpret the first term on the right hand side to be the transformation of freshwater by diahaline mixing that occurs in the interior of the region, G_{int} . It is the convergence of the diffusive salt fluxes. The second term is the surface forced freshwater transformation rate associated with surface source i . Notice how the strength of the surface forced freshwater transformation rate is stronger if the salinity contrast between the incoming waters and the surface waters is stronger, and goes to zero if the salinity of the surface water source has the same salinity as the water mass it is entering. Typically the surface forced freshwater transformation rate (which is associated with the effects of dilution) is much larger than the volumes of low salinity water added (the R_i terms in Eq. (2)). As such, for the purposes of this study we will combine the dilution and volume flux terms in the definition of the surface forced freshwater transformation rate, G_i , such that

$$\begin{aligned} G_i(S) &= (S - S_i) \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial S} + R_i(S) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left[(S - S_i) R_i(S) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

We also consider evaporative, precipitative and run-off fluxes as one freshwater source (G_{epr}) and sea-ice related fluxes (G_{ice}) as a second. The freshwater transformation framework then simplifies to

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{V}}{\partial t} = \Psi + G_{int} + G_{ice} + G_{epr}, \quad (7)$$

where each term is a function of salinity, S .

Fig. 2. (a) Regions as defined for the purpose of this study overlaying the model bathymetry which is based on the SRTM30_PLUS data product (Becker et al., 2009; Korn et al., 2022). (b) Average current speed at 10 m depth during May of model year 55.

Fig. 3. A sketch of the processes involved in the freshwater transformation framework. V is volume of water fresher than some salinity, S ; G_{int} is diahaline volume transport resulting from mixing; G_{surf} is the diahaline transport induced by the addition and dilution of the volume by surface fluxes of freshwater. In this study, G_{surf} is split into a component resulting from sea-ice melt, and evaporation, precipitation and runoff. Ψ corresponds to the steady transport of waters fresher than S into the region and ψ' is the eddy transport. Terms are described in detail in Section 2.

2.1. Interpreting the freshwater transformation framework

The freshwater transformation framework is stated in full in Eq. (7). In Section 4, I apply the framework to outputs from a numerical model and plot each term as a function of salinity in four regions around Greenland. It is useful to briefly explore the physical significance of each term here.

The quantity $\partial_t \mathcal{V}(S)$ describes the rate of change of the volume taken up by waters fresher than salinity S within a region. $\Psi(S)$ gives the total transport of waters with salinity fresher than S into the region. It is an overturning function in salinity space — when non-zero it highlights the freshening or salinification of boundary currents. $G_{int}(S)$ can be thought of as diahaline velocity integrated across the isohaline surface S . Where it is negative, fresh waters are transformed into more saline waters via mixing processes; where it is positive, saline waters are transformed into fresher waters via mixing processes. The $G_i(S)$ terms gives the area integrated transformation of freshwaters forced by surface processes. As with the interior diahaline mixing rates, negative values correspond to the transformation of waters into more saline waters and positive values indicate freshening.

2.2. Application of the freshwater transformation framework to model data

Experience with the water mass transformation framework shows that when working with numerical models it is best to diagnose the budget online, or using the highest frequency model outputs available (Groeskamp et al., 2019). In this work, I calculate the budget using velocity, surface flux, and salinity fields output at daily frequency on the model's native grid.

A strength of freshwater transport frameworks is that they are able to estimate freshwater fluxes resulting from eddies (e.g. Treguier et al., 2014; Mecking et al., 2016). We can attempt to do something similar in the freshwater transformation framework. Consider the time averaged value of $\Psi(S)$ at some section. To calculate this correctly we should perform the calculation online, or with high-frequency (in this study, daily) model outputs. We could also calculate the values of $\Psi(S)$ with low-frequency (in this study, monthly) model outputs. These low-frequency outputs represent the transports associated with the steady flow. One characteristic of eddies is that they are associated with short time-scale motions, so we might choose to describe the difference between the two calculations of Ψ as resulting from eddying motions. Making this more explicit:

$$\langle \psi'(S) \rangle = \iint \langle v_{\perp} H(S - S^*) \rangle dx dz - \iint \langle v_{\perp} \rangle H(\langle S - S^* \rangle) dx dz \quad (8)$$

where $\psi'(S)$ is the eddying transport in salinity space, H is the Heaviside step function, S^* is the salinity at the section and the angled brackets denote monthly averaged quantities.

In this work, the quantity \mathcal{V} is calculated by binning grid-cell volumes by salinity in the desired region, and cumulatively summing along the salinity axis. The temporal derivative is calculated using a centred difference scheme. The G_i terms are calculated by binning surface volume fluxes by sea surface salinity, giving R_i , and then putting this into Eq. (6). The Ψ term is calculated by binning the transport at cell edges by salinity, and cumulatively summing along the salinity axis. To estimate the salinity at cell edges, I linearly interpolate salinity from cell centres to cell edges (required due to the Arakawa C-grid staggering of variables of the model used here). The term G_{int} is calculated as a residual and includes contributions from both parametrized and numerical diahaline mixing. The term could also be diagnosed directly from diffusive salt fluxes (Eq. (5)); however, these were not output in the simulation used here.

2.3. Theoretical successes of the freshwater transformation framework

Having not yet used the framework to generate any new knowledge, it may seem premature to talk of the framework's successes. Nevertheless, from the theoretical exposition of the framework we have just explored, we can begin to see how it addresses the shortcomings of transport based frameworks summarised in the final paragraph of Section 1.3. (The practical successes of the framework will be discussed in Section 5.3.)

The framework's respect for the conservation of mass and salt is built in from the start as can be seen in Eqs. (2) & (3). No reference salinities enter the equations describing the framework, with the terms of the framework instead being treated as functions of salinity (Eq. (7)). The volume transports in salinity space distinguish between low-salinity and saline transports (by definition) and time-averaged transports can be decomposed into steady and eddying components (Eq. (8)). The formation and depletion of reservoirs of low-salinity waters is accounted for by freshwater transformation terms which can be ascribed to various different sources and sinks (Eq. (7)).

3. The ICON model

To demonstrate the power of the freshwater transformation framework, I utilise outputs from the coupled icosahedral non-hydrostatic (ICON) general circulation model developed by the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (Hohenegger et al., 2022; Jungclaus et al., 2022). The ICON model consists of a non-hydrostatic atmospheric component (ICON-Atmosphere) which models both atmospheric and land based components of the earth system (Giorgetta et al., 2018), coupled to a hydrostatic ocean model (ICON-Ocean, Korn, 2017) which incorporates sea-ice dynamics based on the finite element sea-ice model (FESIM, Danilov et al., 2015). The ICON-Ocean model solves the primitive equations on an unstructured Arakawa C-grid under the Boussinesq and hydrostatic approximations (Korn, 2017).

The atmospheric component of the model has an effective resolution of 10 km and 90 vertical levels, whereas the ocean model has a resolution of 5 km and 72 vertical levels, with a z^* coordinate and non-linear free surface (Adcroft and Campin, 2004). In the ocean, the vertical grid-spacing is set to 2 m at the surface and increases to 269.5 m at depth. Model bathymetry is derived from the SRTM30_PLUS dataset (Becker et al., 2009; Korn et al., 2022). Exchanges between the atmospheric and oceanic components of the model are parameterized using the bulk formulae as described in Marsland et al. (2003). The ocean uses a five minute time-step whereas the atmosphere uses a one minute time-step. The model used here builds upon the ICON Sapphire configurations described in Hohenegger et al. (2022). The coupling of the atmosphere to the ocean ensures that mesoscale features in the ocean, such as eddies and boundary currents, interact with the atmosphere in a realistic and self-consistent way. The freshest waters around Greenland are often associated with mesoscale features (such as boundary currents, e.g. Fig. 5) so we want the forcing received by the ocean to be “aware” of their presence (Hirschi et al., 2020).

The UNESCO-80 polynomial equation of state for sea water is used (Gill, 1982). In ICON-Ocean, dissipation of momentum is provided by an adaptive biharmonic Smagorinsky viscosity (Griffies and Hallberg, 2000). The Turbulent Kinetic Energy scheme is used to parameterize the vertical mixing of momentum and tracers (Gaspar et al., 1990).

Liquid water fluxes into and out of the ocean are produced by the atmospheric component of the model. Liquid water is only evaporated when there is no sea-ice. Precipitation can enter the ocean as either snowfall or rainfall. Snowfall enters either the ocean or accumulates over sea-ice. All rainfall enters the surface ocean, regardless of sea-ice cover. Both runoff from land, and sea-ice melt enter into the liquid ocean in surface cells. Precipitation over land is routed by a hydrological discharge scheme and enters the surface ocean as runoff some time

Fig. 4. Average mixed layer depth (a–b) and sea-ice concentration (c–d) during March in the model (left column) and observational products (right column). For the model, the average is taken from model years 50 to 60. The *de Boyer Montégut (2023)* dataset (b) is published as a monthly climatology and is based on data from 1970 to 2020. The OSI climatology (d) is constructed by averaging data from 1979 to 1999 (*OSI SAF, 2017*).

after it has been precipitated (*Hagemann and Dümenil, 1997; Riddick et al., 2018; Reick et al., 2021*). The model does not include interactive ice sheets; rather, they are assumed to be in an approximately steady state. Precipitation over ice sheets is routed by the hydrological discharge scheme to the ocean where it enters as surface runoff, rather than accumulating over land and eventually entering the ocean as a mixture of runoff and meltwater from tidewater (marine terminating) glaciers. The addition of these runoff fluxes into the surface ocean is an inaccuracy, as it is known that freshwater fluxes from tidewater glaciers vary with depth (*Chu, 2014*); however, the dynamics of the melting occur on scales of tens to thousands of metres (*Straneo and Cenedese, 2015; Hewitt, 2020*) — scales finer than the ICON model’s 5 km grid. All volume fluxes have a salinity of 0 g kg^{-1} , except sea-ice melt which has a salinity of 5 g kg^{-1} . The model formulation conserves total salt content, rather than salinity.

The model is initialised with initial conditions based on the EN4 state estimate (*Good et al., 2013*). The present study utilises daily and monthly outputs from simulation years 50 to 60. The model simulates a 1950s climate and has constant greenhouse gas concentrations.

3.1. Model representation of the region

In *Table 1*, mean transports across three key straits in the sub-polar North Atlantic are compared to observational estimates, along with standard deviations which give an indication of the inter-annual variability. Details of the transport calculations are provided in the table caption. At Fram Strait there is good agreement between the

mean summertime transports and observations of *Marnela et al. (2013)*; however, the inter-annual variability is slightly lower in the model than the observations. Note that the model transports are estimated over ten consecutive years whereas the observations are based on four surveys in a thirty year time-span, so it may not be so surprising that the variability in the observations is higher. There is also disagreement between observations as to the strength of the Fram Strait transports, with *Tsubouchi et al. (2024)* estimating the July to September averaged transport to be 1.4 Sv between 2004 and 2010 using mooring data and an inverse box model. Transports and inter-annual variability within Denmark Strait Overflow waters compare very well to observations (*Jochumsen et al., 2017*). Transports at Davis Strait are biased slightly high compared to the observations of *Curry et al. (2014)*, but are still reasonable. The Davis Strait transport also compares well with the estimate of *Tsubouchi et al. (2024)*, who used a box model and moorings to measure a mean 1.9 Sv transport with a standard deviation in the monthly means of 1.0 Sv between 2005 and 2010.

In *Fig. 2b*, I plot daily averaged surface current speeds in the model during May of the 55th year of model integration. The model does a good job of representing the boundary currents around Greenland, and even resolves the double current structures observed off the South East Coast of Greenland *Le Bras et al. (2018), Lin et al. (2018), Gou et al. (2022)* and *Foukal et al. (2020)*. Off North East of Greenland we see a meandering East Greenland Current crossing Fram Strait from the Arctic to the Greenland Sea (*Aagaard and Coachman, 1968a,b; de Steur et al., 2009*). Crossing Fram Strait in the opposite direction is the West Spitsbergen Current (*Aagaard et al., 1987; Rudels et al.,*

Fig. 5. Average wintertime and summertime salinity fields during model years 50 to 60 (left column), in the EN4 state estimate (Good et al., 2013) from 1950 to 1960 (middle column), and their difference (right column). Both model and EN4 salinities are linearly interpolated to a depth of 10 m and 100 m. Nearest neighbour interpolation is used to map the model data to the EN4 grid in the bias plots. EN.4.2.2 data were obtained from <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/> and are © British Crown Copyright, Met Office, 2025, provided under a Non-Commercial Government Licence <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/non-commercial-government-licence/version/2/>.

1999; Walczowski and Piechura, 2011). The East Greenland Current meanders southwards along the coast of Greenland. Around 66°N we see the emergence of an intense current close to the coast of Greenland — the East Greenland Coastal Current (Sutherland and Pickart, 2008; Bacon et al., 2014). Note that although the current is well resolved, due to its width and the model's large biharmonic viscosity (required for numerical stability) the current is likely overly laminar. Observations indicate that the East Greenland Coastal Current also exists north of Denmark Strait (Foukal et al., 2020; Le Bras et al., 2018) but in the model this pathway is somewhat weak and intermittent. South of Denmark Strait, the Irminger Current merges with the East Greenland Current and sits offshore of the East Greenland Coastal Current. The Irminger Current follows the topography from the Southern Irminger Sea along the Reykjanes Ridge towards Denmark Strait (Fried and de Jong, 2022), and then follows the coast of East Greenland towards Cape Farewell (Daniault et al., 2011; Le Bras et al., 2018; Petit et al., 2019) — qualitatively, the model resolves this pathway well. Upon rounding

Cape Farewell, the East Greenland Coastal Current and Irminger Current form the West Greenland Current (Myers et al., 2007). The current follows the bathymetry away from Greenland, rimming the Labrador Sea (Lozier, 2023), although eddies have been observed to transport waters away from the coast south of the 3,000 m isobath (Myers et al., 2007, 2009; Pacini and Pickart, 2022) — indeed, this can be seen in the eddy rich region at $60 \pm 2.5^\circ\text{N}$ and $50 \pm 2.5^\circ\text{W}$ in Fig. 2b. The modelled currents in Baffin Bay are weaker, in qualitative agreement with observations (Tang et al., 2004; Münchow et al., 2015). The model also reproduces a strong current bringing waters from the Arctic through Nares Strait (Rabe et al., 2012; Münchow, 2016) and southwards along the western edge of Baffin Bay.

In Fig. 4a I show the mean March mixed layer depth from the model between the 50th and 60th year of model integration, accompanied by a mixed layer depth climatology in Fig. 4b (de Boyer Montégut, 2023; de Boyer Montégut et al., 2004). I define the mixed layer depth as the depth at which the density increases by 0.03 kg m^{-3} relative to the

Table 1
Mean transports and sample standard deviations across key model sections compared to observational estimates.

Section	Model (Sv)	Observations (Sv)	Source
Fram Strait ^a	2.6 ± 0.7	3.1 ± 1.3	Marnela et al. (2013)
Denmark Strait Overflow ^b	3.3 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.2	Jochumsen et al. (2017)
Davis Strait ^c	2.2 ± 0.4	1.6 ± 0.2	Curry et al. (2014)

^a At Fram Strait, the stated model transport is the July average during model years 50 to 60 and the sample standard deviation is that of the ten July averages. The observational estimate of Marnela et al. (2013) is based on four hydrographic surveys from summertime 1984, 1997, 2002 and 2004 and the sample standard deviation is that of the four averages (see table 2 of Marnela et al., 2013).

^b Transports at Denmark Strait are of waters with $\sigma_\theta > 27.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The stated model transport is the average during model years 50 to 60 and the sample standard deviation is that of the ten annual averages. The observational estimate of Jochumsen et al. (2017) is based on moored observations from 1997 to 2012, with the sample standard deviation calculated from the 24 annual averages.

^c At Davis Strait, the stated model transport is the average during model years 50 to 60 and the sample standard deviation is that of the ten annual averages. The observational estimate of Curry et al. (2014) is based on moored observations from 2004 to 2010, with the sample standard deviation calculated from the six annual means (see table 2 of Curry et al., 2014). Locations of all model sections are shown in Fig. 2a.

density at 10 m. Spatially, the representation of deep mixed layers is very good, with deep mixed layers found in the Southern Labrador & Irminger Seas, and between Jan-Mayen Island and Svalbard. The mixed layers around Jan-Mayen Island extend slightly too far westwards to the Greenland shelf; however, the regions considered in this study are all onshore of the shelf-break. The deepest mixed layer depths are deeper in the model than in the climatology and I speculate that this is associated with too weak salinity stratification in the model (visible in the surface intensified salinity bias, Fig. 5). Other sources of bias may be the definition of mixed layer depth I employ, which has been reported to overestimate mixed layer depths in models (Courtois et al., 2017); or the observational product itself, with some of the mixed layer depth estimates in the Labrador Sea relying on fewer than 25 observations (de Boyer Montégut, 2023).

The modelled March sea-ice cover in the western Arctic and off the West coast of Greenland looks very good (Figs. 4c & d). On the east coast of Greenland the sea-ice cover is fair, with open water forming at the Eastern edge of Fram Strait, and very low sea-ice cover in the coastal region south of Denmark Strait. Sea-ice cover in the Barents Sea and Kara Sea is low; however, this is relatively distant from the study region. Across the study region (see the shaded areas in Fig. 2a) the annual mean melt rate of sea-ice is 44 mSv compared to a formation rate of 24 mSv implying a net import of approximately 20 mSv (assuming the annual mean sea-ice volume within the region remains roughly the same in the 10 year period under consideration). Annually averaged runoff from the modelled Greenland ice-sheet contributes around 70% of the liquid freshwater flux from sea-ice, inputting 31 mSv of runoff — this is close to observed estimates of 26 mSv from between 1959 and 1979 (Bamber et al., 2018). There is an annual cycle in rates of runoff around Greenland, with Bamber et al. (2018) estimating the range of the monthly average runoff rates to be around 75 mSv. The model does not accurately capture this (likely due to the absence of an interactive ice sheet model), with a range in the monthly averaged runoff rates of 30 mSv. Were the freshwater transformation framework applied to a model which better captures the seasonality of runoff rates, we may see stronger freshwater transformation rates from runoff during summer and associated down-stream impacts.

In Fig. 5, I compare the modelled salinity fields at 10 m and 100 m depth during summertime and wintertime with the EN4 data product (Good et al., 2013) — note that this is the same data product used to initialise the model prior to the 50 year spin-up. At 10 m depth, there appear to be fresh biases along the eastern coast of Greenland, and smaller biases on the shelf break. These biases persist at 100 m and their seasonal cycle is small. Given the coarseness of the EN4 data

product ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$) and the interpolation used in its production, it would be expected that it does not pick up low salinity extremes over the continental shelf which are present in the model (Good et al., 2013). On the other hand, the high salinity bias in the Labrador Sea and the fresh bias in Baffin Bay are likely real. Nevertheless, the biases in the ICON configuration described here compare well to the ensemble averaged biases seen in CMIP6 models (see for example figure 3.23 of Eyring et al., 2021). Note also that high salinity biases over the Labrador Sea have been observed and investigated in other high-resolution models (e.g. Koenigk et al., 2021; Rattan et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2024).

Further plots showing the modelled winds, heat-fluxes and precipitation across the sub-polar North Atlantic are shown in the supplementary materials. The modelled fields compare well to the ERA5 reanalysis product (Hersbach et al., 2023).

4. The freshwater transformation framework applied to Greenland's coastal regions

4.1. Definition of regions

The freshwater transformation framework requires us to define discrete, bounded volumes around the coast of Greenland. For the purpose of this study I define four regions bounded by ten different sections. The regions are shown in Fig. 2c. The regions are approximately bounded by the 1000 m isobath in the along-shore direction, with the across-shore sections following great circles. The sections enclosing the regions are defined on the model's native grid and the procedure for constructing the sections is described in Appendix A. All calculations in what follows correspond to averages over model years 50 to 60 and take place on the model's native grid.

4.2. North East Greenland

Fig. 6a shows each of the terms in the freshwater transformation budget as a function of salinity for a region off North East Greenland during wintertime. We see a depletion in the volume of waters fresher than around 32.6 g kg^{-1} (green line) at a rate of 0.8 Sv. This is driven in roughly equal measures by freshwater transformation from sea-ice formation (blue line) and mixing (orange line). There is a small net import of low salinity waters into the region (purple line) which tempers the rate of volume depletion (green line). Approximately 0.8 Sv of mixing induced transport, directed from saline to fresh, across the 34.5 g kg^{-1} isohaline combines with 0.4 Sv of sea-ice melt to freshen the more saline components of the boundary currents and increase the volume of waters fresher than 34.5 g kg^{-1} in the region. In Fig. 6c we break down the transport into the region by section. We see that the freshest waters entering across Fram strait (solid pink line) are fresher than those leaving the region across Denmark Strait (solid olive line). There is some import of waters saltier than around 33 g kg^{-1} across the North East section (solid blue line). This may in part be due to the meandering of currents crossing Fram Strait (see Fig. 2b); and in part due to ice-ocean stresses forcing fresh waters onshore (Spall et al., 2024). During wintertime, there is an export by eddies of around 0.3 Sv of waters in the salinity class $33.75\text{--}34.5 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ across the North East section (dashed blue line). At Denmark Strait, the circulation exports around 0.1 Sv of water fresher than 33.25 g kg^{-1} out of the region and a similar amount of water is imported into the region with a salinity of between $33.25\text{--}33.75 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ (dashed olive line). Although small in magnitude compared to the total export at the section, this is around 50% of the net import of water fresher than 32.5 g kg^{-1} into the region as a whole.

During summertime, sea-ice melt acts to increase the volume of low salinity waters in the region (Fig. 6b, blue line). In the freshest salinity classes, this melt water input is balanced almost perfectly by mixing

Fig. 6. Freshwater transformation budget (see Eq. (7)) during (a) winter and (b) summer, calculated from daily model outputs between simulation years 50 and 60 for the North East region. Below, (c–d) the salinity space transports over the same period are broken down by section. Solid lines indicate steady transports and dashed lines indicate eddy transports (see Eq. (8)). Line color indicates the section location as mapped in panel (e). Note that the term $\Psi(S)$ in panels (a–b) and the transport terms in panels (c–d) are transports of waters fresher than salinity S . Similarly, the term $\partial_t \mathcal{V}$ is the tendency of the volume fresher than salinity S . Transformation rates, G , give volume fluxes across isohaline surfaces, with positive fluxes directed from saline to fresh. Light olive and light pink lines indicate transports across the “full” Denmark Strait and Fram Strait sections, which stretch from Greenland to Iceland and Svalbard, respectively and are discussed further in section Section 4.2.

(orange line), which transforms the low salinity waters into more saline waters. Interior diahaline mixing (orange line), sea-ice melt (blue line) and net lateral imports (purple line) of low salinity waters leads to an inflation in the volume of waters fresher than 32.75 g kg^{-1} at a rate of 0.4 Sv (green line). The lateral imports of low salinity waters come predominantly from across Fram Strait and the North East section (Fig. 6d, pink and blue lines) with the freshest waters within the boundary currents becoming saltier by the time they reach Denmark Strait (olive line). The volume of waters with salinities between $32.7\text{--}34.5 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$

decreases during summertime, largely driven by the export of these waters across Denmark Strait. Eddies are responsible for smaller volume transports across the North East section during summertime than in wintertime; however, the transports are fresher. Spall et al. (2024) find that offshore eddy fluxes of freshwater during summertime are stronger than in wintertime; however, they consider freshwater transports to draw this conclusion. It is plausible that these two sets of findings are compatible; however, note that the salinity space transports provide extra information, telling us that although summertime eddy transports

Fig. 7. Freshwater transformation budget (see Eq. (7)) during (a) winter and (b) summer, calculated from daily model outputs between simulation years 50 and 60 for the South East region. Below, (c–d) the salinity space transports over the same period are broken down by section. Solid lines indicate steady transports and dashed lines indicate eddy transports (see Eq. (8)). Line color indicates the section location as mapped in panel (e). Note that the term $\Psi(S)$ in panels (a–b) and the transport terms in panels (c–d) are transports of waters fresher than salinity S . Similarly, the term $\partial_t \mathcal{V}$ is the tendency of the volume fresher than salinity S . Transformation rates, G , give volume fluxes across isohaline surfaces, with positive fluxes directed from saline to fresh.

are smaller than in winter the salinity of these transports is much reduced.

Karpouzoglou et al. (2023) examine the seasonality of freshwater transport at Fram Strait. They find freshwater transport is large in summer, peaks in October and is then smaller in winter, reaching a minimum in April. Looking at the transports across the whole of Fram Strait (Figs. 6c–d, light pink line), we see that their result can be explained by fresher waters crossing the strait during summertime than in wintertime.

de Steur et al. (2017) look at the seasonality of freshwater transports at Denmark Strait. They find that in wintertime, anomalously strong currents and salty waters crossing the section counteract each other; whereas, during summertime anomalously fresh waters and weak currents counteract each other. Qualitatively, this is visible in the light olive lines of Fig. 6c–d. During wintertime there is a higher volume of low salinity waters crossing Denmark Strait; however, during summertime the currents are weaker but contain fresher waters.

4.3. South East Greenland

During wintertime, off the coast of South East Greenland we see salinification of the freshest waters carried by the boundary currents as they travel from Denmark Strait to the western edge of the OSNAP East line (Fig. 7c, olive and pink lines). The salinification is driven by diahaline mixing which exports waters across the 33.1 g kg^{-1} isohaline at a rate of 1.4 Sv (Fig. 7a, orange line). Fresh waters transformed by sea-ice melt (0.7 Sv of water fresher than 33.1 g kg^{-1} , blue line) are also salinified by the mixing. We see a resultant increase in the volume of waters more saline than 32.9 g kg^{-1} (green line). That sea-ice related fluxes are acting to freshen the region during wintertime may at first seem surprising. The freshening occurs as there is little sea-ice formation South of Davis Strait in the model, with most sea-ice being advected from the North East Region. Much of this sea-ice then melts in the waters off South East Greenland. (Note that the freshwater transformation from sea-ice, G_{ice} , does not correspond to just the liquid freshwater flux, but also the dilution of waters it is added to. The 0.6 Sv of transformation results from a much smaller volume flux of liquid sea-ice melt.)

During summertime, the freshest waters crossing Denmark Strait have a similar (though slightly saltier) salinity when they leave the region via the western edge of the OSNAP East line (Fig. 7d, olive & pink lines). The predominant surface source of freshwater during this time is precipitation and runoff, but the term remains weak (Fig. 7b, red line). We would expect this term to be larger if the model represented the seasonal cycle in Greenland runoff. By summertime the majority of the sea-ice in this region has gone and so there is virtually no freshwater transformation driven by sea-ice melt (blue line). Persistently strong diahaline mixing during summertime in this region leads to the depletion of low salinity waters (orange & green lines); whereas, in the North East we see weaker mixing and an accumulation of low salinity waters at this time of year (Fig. 6b, orange & green lines).

Le Bras et al. (2021) describe the circulation around Greenland as having two components: a fresh estuarine circulation and an overturning circulation associated with the salinification of freshwaters. They estimate that around 50% of the polar waters crossing Fram Strait participate in the overturning circulation before reaching Cape Farewell; and that 60% of the surface freshwater added off the east coast of Greenland contributes to the overturning. Off North East Greenland we saw very weak boundary current salinification in the freshest water mass classes; however, off South East Greenland we see strong salinification of the waters crossing Denmark Strait during wintertime — of the 1.1 Sv of steady and 0.1 Sv of eddy imports of water fresher than 33.5 g kg^{-1} entering the region via Denmark Strait, 0.7 Sv leave at Cape Farewell having been salinified. During summertime the salinification in this area is much weaker. Our methodology is not directly comparable with that of Le Bras et al. (2021); however, our result suggests that the polar waters that participate in the overturning circulation are largely transformed south of Denmark Strait, with their formation rates being especially strong during wintertime and their salinification being driven by mixing rather than surface freshwater fluxes.

Along the whole coast of Eastern Greenland we see near-zero volumes of low salinity water crossing the 1000 m isobath. This is consistent with the findings of Duyck and De Jong (2023).

4.4. South West Greenland

During wintertime, off South West Greenland, the salinity of waters imported around Cape Farewell are fresher than those exported into the Labrador Sea and across Davis Strait (Fig. 8c) — the boundary currents onshore of the 1000 m isobath are salinified. Almost all of this salinification is driven by diahaline mixing (Fig. 8a, orange line). The diahaline mixing rates in this region are small; however, it should

be noted that the area of this region is much smaller than the others, due to the narrowness of the shelf.

Eddy transports of low salinity waters across the 1000 m isobath are large in this region, with 0.4 Sv of waters fresher than 34.5 g kg^{-1} crossing the shelf in both wintertime and summertime (Fig. 8c & d, dashed blue lines). In some salinity classes the eddy transports of low salinity waters exceed the steady transports during the summer. There is a strong seasonal cycle in the salinities of the waters entering and leaving the region, with summertime steady imports from around Cape Farewell (solid pink line) and exports across Davis Strait (solid olive line) freshening, whereas steady exports to the interior of the Labrador sea become saltier (solid blue line). During summertime the freshest waters are exported across Davis Strait rather than into the Labrador Sea (olive and blue lines). Overall, there is little change in the salinity of the boundary currents as they pass through the region during summertime (Fig. 8b, purple line). There is still some diahaline mixing occurring (orange line); however, this acts to mix freshwater sourced from precipitation and runoff (red line).

Pacini and Pickart (2022) highlight the important role of eddies in transporting waters out of the West Greenland Current and into the Labrador Sea — something that we also see in our model. They note that eddy activity (as measured by eddy kinetic energy) in the region is higher during wintertime than summertime, which may at first seem to contradict the relatively similar eddy exports of low salinity waters we see across the South West section during both wintertime and summertime. There is however seasonality in the import of saline waters from the Labrador Sea by eddies: during wintertime 0.8 Sv of water with salinities between $34.8\text{--}35.0 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ is imported by eddies, compared to 0.4 Sv during summertime (not shown in Fig. 8). The end result may well be stronger eddy driven “freshwater exports” in wintertime than summertime; however, the salinity space transports have revealed that this is driven by eddies fluxing salt water onshore rather than freshwater offshore.

Sections taken by Curry et al. (2014) across Davis Strait are consistent with the salinity space transports seen here: they observe stronger and fresher currents at the Eastern boundary of Davis Strait during summertime than in wintertime.

The maximum in salinity space transports across the OSNAP West line has been estimated from observations to be 12 Sv of northward transports of waters fresher than 34.9 g kg^{-1} between August 2014 and April 2016 (Zou et al., 2020). In the model, we find a weaker transport of 6 Sv ; however, the salinity of maximum overturning is found to be 34.9 g kg^{-1} , in good agreement with the observations. (The streamfunction at the OSNAP West line is not shown here.)

4.5. North West Greenland

Off North West Greenland (the eastern side of Baffin Bay), the volume of low salinity waters decreases during the winter months (Fig. 9a, green line). This is driven by the export of fresh waters (predominantly at the Northern edge of the region, purple line), diahaline mixing (orange line) and brine rejection from sea-ice formation (blue line). The export suggests boundary currents are freshened as they travel through the region. Fig. 9a indicates this is the result of fresh waters being mixed into the boundary currents.

During summertime, the volume of low salinity waters in the region grows again (Fig. 9b, green line). Fluxes from evaporation, precipitation and runoff transform the freshest waters (fresher than 31 g kg^{-1} , red line), which are then mixed (orange line), leading to an increase in the volume of waters fresher than 32.25 g kg^{-1} . There is also a net import of low salinity waters, resulting from fresher inflows across Davis Strait (Fig. 9d, olive line) and a decrease in the freshwater export at the Northern edge of the region relative to wintertime (pink line).

The seasonal cycle in the volume of low salinity waters off North West Greenland mirrors what is seen in salinity sections in the region (e.g. figure 12 of Tang et al., 2004). At Davis Strait, Tang et al.

Fig. 8. Freshwater transformation budget (see Eq. (7)) during (a) winter and (b) summer, calculated from daily model outputs between simulation years 50 and 60 for the South West region. Below, (c–d) the salinity space transports over the same period are broken down by section. Solid lines indicate steady transports and dashed lines indicate eddy transports (see Eq. (8)). Line color indicates the section location as mapped in panel (e). Note that the term $\Psi(S)$ in panels (a–b) and the transport terms in panels (c–d) are transports of waters fresher than salinity S . Similarly, the term $\partial_t \mathcal{V}$ is the tendency of the volume fresher than salinity S . Transformation rates, G , give volume fluxes across isohaline surfaces, with positive fluxes directed from saline to fresh.

(2004) see a downward displacement of 34 g kg^{-1} isohaline between June and August driven by an expansion of the volume of fresher waters. Using the freshwater transformation framework we can ascribe this to the addition of very fresh waters into the region by evaporative, precipitative and runoff fluxes, which are then mixed with saltier waters. The volume of waters between the $33\text{--}34 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ isohalines remains relatively constant, with the waters freshened by mixing replaced by imports from across Davis Strait in the model.

Shan et al. (2024) estimate surface forced *water mass* transformation rates in Baffin Bay from a regional model from October to April and

May to September. They find strong densification during autumn & winter and weak lightening in spring & summer; however, they do not break down the rates by buoyancy source. Although buoyancy fluxes are distinct from salinity fluxes, the freshwater transformation framework seems to suggest that sea-ice formation plays an important role in wintertime densification (heat fluxes across the region will be small due to the insulating effect of sea-ice cover). However, sea-ice melt plays a far less important role in summertime lightening of waters. Freshening is driven by evaporation, precipitation and runoff (and in this model is likely underestimated due to the suppressed seasonal

Fig. 9. Freshwater transformation budget (see Eq. (7)) during (a) winter and (b) summer, calculated from daily model outputs between simulation years 50 and 60 for the North West region. Below, (c–d) the salinity space transports over the same period are broken down by section. Solid lines indicate steady transports and dashed lines indicate eddy transports (see Eq. (8)). Line color indicates the section location as mapped in panel (e). Note that the term $\Psi(S)$ in panels (a–b) and the transport terms in panels (c–d) are transports of waters fresher than salinity S . Similarly, the term $\partial_t \mathcal{V}$ is the tendency of the volume fresher than salinity S . Transformation rates, G , give volume fluxes across isohaline surfaces, with positive fluxes directed from saline to fresh.

cycle in runoff rates) with heat fluxes potentially also influencing the buoyancy budget.

5. Synthesis

We have explored how traditional freshwater budgets based around ideas of freshwater content and freshwater transports can provide limited insights when exploring the fate of low salinity waters as they are added and removed from the ocean — freshwater transports cannot distinguish between exports of low salinity waters and imports

of saline waters into a region; and the budgets cannot identify where low salinity waters are mixed. We then introduced the freshwater transformation framework (based upon the same principles as the water mass transformation framework of Walin, 1982) which provided us with a new vocabulary with which to discuss the fate of freshwater. In this framework, freshwater transports are replaced by salinity space transports ($\psi(S)$) and surface freshwater fluxes are replaced by freshwater transformation rates ($G(S)$) which we can assign to processes such as evaporation, precipitation, runoff, sea-ice melt and diahaline mixing.

Fig. 10. Area corrected diahaline mixing rates for each region during (a) winter and (b) summer. When correcting for area, we divide the diahaline mixing rate, \bar{G}_{mi} , by the area of the region and multiply by the area of the South East region.

5.1. Spatio-temporal dependence of diahaline mixing rates

In Sections 4.2 to 4.5 we demonstrated the framework on outputs from an eddy rich coupled general circulation model and used it to explore the fate of freshwater around Greenland. A key finding of the framework is the strong spatio-temporal dependence of the mixing of freshwaters as indicated by diahaline mixing rates. Strong seasonal cycles in sea-ice melt and formation, and Greenland runoff are relatively well understood; however, the seasonality in rates of diahaline mixing (which is distinct from diapycnal mixing) has not before been mapped out. Fig. 10 shows diahaline mixing rates for each of the regions considered here during wintertime and summertime, but normalised by the area of the region. Firstly, one will note how much stronger salinification by diahaline mixing is during wintertime than summertime. Observations off the east coast of Greenland have shown that during wintertime, the cooling of surface waters is often accompanied by their salinification. When cooled, surface waters sink and become surrounded by warmer saltier waters; meaning subsequent along isopycnal mixing results in a diahaline transport (Le Bras et al., 2018). This diahaline mixing mechanism requires strong surface buoyancy fluxes, which typically occur during wintertime. Secondly, one will note that the shapes of the diahaline mixing curves vary with region. Area normalised rates of diahaline mixing during wintertime are greatest off South West and South East Greenland, regions with low sea-ice cover. Sea-ice insulates surface waters from atmospheric heat fluxes meaning thermally driven diahaline mixing rates off Northern Greenland will be smaller. Future work should investigate this hypothesis further.

5.2. Implications for the hosing experiment

Regardless of the cause of the spatio-temporal variability in diahaline mixing rates, the variability is consequential for those studying the response of the climate system to the melting of the Greenland ice sheet in models. We have seen that the eventual fate of freshwater depends upon where and when it is added around Greenland; implying that, in models, ice-sheet melt fluxes should be realistically placed in space and time. In the NAHosMIP a “more realistic set of Greenland-hosing experiments” were proposed in which a temporally uniform 100 mSv of freshwater is added around Greenland¹ (Jackson et al.,

¹ Note that 100 mSv is an upper estimate of plausible ice-sheet melt under anthropogenic climate change scenarios (Swingedouw et al., 2007).

2023). Given what we have seen here, I would argue that this type of hosing pattern may still lead to unrealistic responses in the climate system, in particular to the AMOC, due to its temporal uniformity.

Let us try and understand the potential effects of temporally uniform hosing on the AMOC. Le Bras et al. (2021) & Eldevik and Nilsen (2013) talk of the sub-polar circulation being made up of a fresh estuarine circulation in which freshwaters added to the region remain fresh, and an overturning circulation in which freshwaters are mixed and impact the AMOC. Qualitatively, our results suggest that freshwater added to the ocean during summertime are more likely to join the estuarine circulation; whereas freshwater added to the ocean during wintertime will join the overturning circulation (see for example the diahaline mixing rates shown in Fig. 10). Due to summer intensified melt rates from the Greenland ice-sheet (Bamber et al., 2018) we may expect too much freshwater to join the overturning and too little freshwater to join the estuarine circulation in a model with temporally uniform hosing, resulting in an overly sensitive AMOC. An assumption in this reasoning is that diahaline mixing patterns under hosing continue to resemble those under the mean climate. This may not hold, especially as we suspect the patterns are sensitive to sea-ice cover and the climate system is known to be non-linear. The running of further experiments is required, and their results may reveal a need to use high spatio-temporal resolution projections of Greenland ice-sheet runoff, such as those of Schmidt et al. (2025), when investigating the climate’s response to enhanced ice-sheet runoff.

5.3. Practical successes of the freshwater transformation framework

In Section 2.3 we discussed the theoretical successes of the freshwater transformation framework. Having now applied the framework we can assess how useful it has been in garnering new knowledge about the fate of freshwater. In my view, the biggest success of the framework has been its ability to quantify how rates of diahaline mixing vary with season and location around Greenland (Section 5.1) — this has not been done before. The result comes with the usual caveats about model limitations; however, application of the framework to other models (or better still, observations) will add certainty to what we have seen here.

A further success has been the linking of surface processes to diahaline mixing rates and boundary current salinity changes. These links are highly dependent upon season and region and so readers are directed to Sections 4.2 to 4.5 for detailed discussion of these results. An interesting finding was the relatively weak seasonality in eddy transports of low salinity waters away from South West Greenland despite wintertime

peaks in eddy activity (Schulze Chretien and Frajka-Williams, 2018; Pacini and Pickart, 2022; Morrison et al., 2024). Instead we noted the seasonality manifested itself in eddy transports of saline waters onshore (Section 4.4).

5.4. Application of the freshwater transformation framework to observational data

Having successfully applied the freshwater transformation framework to model data, a natural question is how can we use it in observations? I see two key obstacles to being able to apply the framework in full: firstly, we have seen that over seasonal time-scales the $\partial_t \mathcal{V}$ term is not only non-zero but also non-negligible. To calculate this requires a census of the low salinity waters in the region, a non-trivial exercise. Secondly, in calculating the surface forced freshwater transformation rates, we need to know the sea surface salinity. As we have seen, sea-ice melt and formation is a dominant driver of freshwater transformation around Greenland. Obtaining either in-situ or remotely sensed estimates of sea surface salinity under sea-ice is a further non-trivial endeavour. Tsubouchi et al. (2012, 2018, 2024) use box inverse models to calculate water mass transformation rates across the Arctic based on boundary observations. Modifying their methods to allow the calculation of freshwater transformation rates seems a promising avenue for further research. I suspect salinity space transports will be the easiest component of the freshwater transformation framework to evaluate from observations. Indeed, salinity space transports are already reported at OSNAP West (Zou et al., 2020) and many of the studies cited in this work produce interpolated transport and salinity sections before converting them to volume and freshwater transports. Converting such products to salinity space transports is a trivial task.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Constructing regions and sections on an unstructured grid

The ICON model makes use of an unstructured Arakawa C-grid. Scalar variables are defined at the centres of triangular cells; whereas, velocities are defined at the edges of these cells. To calculate the modelled transport across a section, we must construct a path on the model grid which follows the grid edges. We begin to construct these

Table A.2

Table of sections indicating the type of the section and the weights used in its construction.

Section	Section type	Target depth contour (m)	Smoothing factor (m)
Fram Strait	Great-circle	–	0
North East	Isobath	1000	2500
Denmark Strait	Great-circle	–	0
South East	Isobath	1000	750
Cape Farewell East	Great-circle	–	0
Cape Farewell West	Great-circle	–	0
South West	Isobath	1000	1000
Davis Strait	Great-circle	–	0
Baffin Bay Central	Isobath	1000	1000
Baffin Bay North	Great-circle	–	0

paths by representing the model grid as a graph, with the vertices of the triangular grid forming nodes and the edges of the grid forming the edges of the graph. If one wanted to find the shortest path between two points, one could simply use the edge lengths as the weights of the graph and apply a path finding algorithm (in this study we use Dijkstra’s algorithm Dijkstra, 1959). We are often interested in more complicated sections than simply the shortest path across a strait — we may for instance wish to construct a section which follows the model’s bathymetry or approximates a great-circle (as we did in this study). This can be done via the use of different types of weights for the graph, the choice of which is detailed below.

The routines used to construct the paths used in this study have been packaged, documented and made available in the python package ICONSPy (ICON Sections in Python; Goldsworth, 2025).

A.1. Isobathymetric paths

To construct a path which approximately follows a depth contour, we can use the absolute value of the model depth at an edge subtracted from the target model depth as a weight (similar processes can be used to construct paths which follow any contour). Applying Dijkstra’s algorithm will then generate a path approximating the isobath. Sometimes these paths follow the contour very tightly and we may wish to remove some of its “wiggles”. One way of doing this is by adding a constant smoothing factor to the weights of every edge. A large smoothing factor penalises paths which follow a large number of edges and so the path finding algorithm will return paths with fewer edges and which are smoother. Mathematically, the weights at each edge, w_e are given by

$$w_e = \left| h_e - H_{target} \right| + c_{smooth}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where h_e is the depth at the edge, H_{target} is the target depth and c_{smooth} is the smoothing factor. The target depth and smoothing factors for each of the paths considered in this study is shown in Table A.2. The large smoothing factor used in producing the North East section was required to remove undesirable features that appear when the 1000 m contour breaks at Denmark Strait.

A.2. Great-circle paths

The shortest path connecting two grid points is often not a great-circle (shortest paths typically minimise the number of edges traversed). When constructing great-circle paths, we use the angular distance between an edge and the ‘analytical’ great-circle as weights. The path which minimises these weights approximates the great circle.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2025.102599>.

Data availability

The dataset used in this study was produced using the ICON general circulation model (Jungclaus et al., 2022). An open source release of the model is published by the ICON partnership (DWD; MPI-M; DKRZ; KIT; C2SM, 2024). Code and processed data used in this study are available for download at <https://doi.org/10.17617/3.X2LOBR> (Goldsworth, 2024).

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